

Thiocyanato Substituted Nitrosyl Chromium(I) Complexes

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Manuscript received 20 April 1981, accepted 7 January 1982

A new series of thiocyanato substituted nitrosyl chromium(I) having square based pyramidal and octahedral stereochemistry around the metal ion with the general formula, $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})]$ and $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})(\text{py})]$ respectively (where B=2,2' dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline) have been isolated and characterised by analysis, conductance, magnetic measurements, electron spin resonance and infrared spectral studies.

A survey of literature on neutral penta and hexa-coordinated nitrosyl chromium(I) complexes reveals that reports on such complexes are but very few¹⁻³. Recently we prepared and characterised some neutral cyano substituted nitrosyl-chromium(I) complexes* and this study prompted us to characterise the thiocyanato substituted complexes. We report in this communication the preparation, properties and characterisation of some thiocyanato substituted nitrosyl chromium(I) complexes of composition, $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})]$ and $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})(\text{py})]$ (B=2,2' dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline). The complexes have been characterised by analysis, conductance, magnetic measurements, electron spin resonance and infrared spectral studies.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade. Deaerated water was used in all operations.

Preparation of diisothiocyanato dipyridyl nitrosyl-chromium(I) $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})]$: 1.0 g of K_2CrO_4 and 3.8 g of KCNS were taken in a beaker and 40 ml of water was added to dissolve the mixture. 1.0 g of $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$ was slowly added into the solution with stirring. A vigorous reaction sets in and hence addition of $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$ was done cautiously to control the temperature (further addition leads to the expulsion of NO). After the addition of $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$, the reaction mixture was stirred for 1 hr and any grey colour precipitate was allowed to dissolve by adding dilute acetic acid dropwise. To the filtered green solution, 0.78 g of dipyridyl dissolved in dilute acetic acid was added. A Khaki colour precipitate appeared which was stirred for 1 hr at a temperature around 90° and filtered. The precipitate was washed several times with dilute acetic acid, finally washed with water, dried in air and recrystallised from methanol-petroleum ether. The yield was approximately 45%. Anal. Found: Cr, 14.6; C, 40.5; N, 19.7; H, 2.1; S, 18.1. Calcd. for $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})]$; Cr, 14.7; C, 40.7; N, 19.8; H, 2.2; S, 18.0%.

Preparation of diisothiocyanato *o*-phenanthroline-nitrosylchromium(I), $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{o-phen})]$: The

corresponding *o*-phenanthroline complex was prepared analogously as described above by replacing dipyridyl with *o*-phenanthroline. The olive green recrystallised compound was analysed. Anal. Found: Cr, 13.6; C, 44.2; N, 18.3; H, 2.1; S, 16.8. Calcd. for $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{o-phen})]$; Cr, 13.8; C, 44.4; N, 18.5; H, 2.1; S, 16.9%.

Preparation of diisothiocyanato dipyridylpyridine-nitrosylchromium(I), $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})(\text{py})]$: About 0.5 g of $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})]$ was dissolved in 15 ml of acetone and 1 ml of pyridine was added into it. The solution was refluxed for about 2 hr on water bath with positive pressure of the inside solvent vapour (using a pool of mercury) and the resultant solution was vacuum concentrated. The product was isolated from the solution by adding petroleum ether as yellow solid which was recrystallised from acetone-petroleum ether mixture. The yield was approximately 75%. Anal. Found: Cr, 11.9; C, 47.0; N, 19.2; H, 2.9; S, 14.6. Calcd. for $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})(\text{py})]$; Cr, 12.0; C, 47.1; N, 19.4; H, 3.0; S, 14.8%.

Preparation of diisothiocyanato *o*-phenanthroline-pyridine nitrosylchromium(I), $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{o-phen})(\text{py})]$: The *o*-phenanthroline analogue of the previous compound was prepared analogously as described earlier, by taking $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{o-phen})]$ instead of $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})]$. The yellow reprecipitated compound from acetone-petroleum ether mixture was dried and analysed. Anal. Found: Cr, 11.3; C, 49.8; N, 18.2; H, 2.7; S, 13.9. Calcd. for $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{o-phen})(\text{py})]$; Cr, 11.4; C, 49.9; N, 18.4; H, 2.8; S, 14.0%.

Analysis: Chromium was determined as Cr_2O_3 after decomposing the complexes by heating with alkali followed by dissolving in HNO_3 and precipitating by NH_4OH . C, H and N were determined microanalytically. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 after completely oxidising the aqueous suspension of the complexes with Br_2 water on water bath followed by acidification with dilute HCl and precipitating the sulphate with BaCl_2 solution.

Physical methods: Conductance was measured in analytical grade methanol using a dip type cell with the help of Philips conductivity bridge

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TABLE 1—IMPORTANT IR SPECTRAL BANDS AND ASSIGNMENTS*

Compound	$\nu(\text{NO}^+)$	$\nu(\text{CN})$	Organic ligand	$\nu(\text{CrN})$	$\nu(\text{CrNO})$
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})]$	1700s	2070vs	1600m, 1576w, 1500m, 1480m, 1440s, 1372w, 1308m, 1295w, 1250w, 1210w, 1165w, 1150w, 1084w, 1070w, 1025w, 1010m, 760s, 715m, 600w.	620w	595w
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(o\text{-phen})]$	1710s	2070vs	1440w, 1415m, 1340w, 1220w, 1145w, 1105w, 880w, 845m, 765m, 740w, 710m, 685w, 650w.	600w	565w
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})(\text{py})]$	1710s	2075vs	1602m, 1575w, 1495m, 1475m, 1438w, 1310m, 1296w, 1245w, 1215w, 1170w, 1148w, 1088w, 1050w, 1020w, 1014m, 800w, 756s, 716w, 600w, 570w.	625w	592w
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(o\text{-phen})(\text{py})]$	1710s	2080vs	1615w, 1535w, 1515w, 1451w, 1425m, 1340w, 1315w, 1220w, 1210w, 1180w, 1145w, 1107w, 1095w, 875w, 845m, 835w, 770w, 740w, 725m, 685m, 650m, 605m, 460w, 440w.	620m	570w

* Positions (cm^{-1}) and relative intensities (vs, very strong; s, strong; m, medium; w, weak).

apparatus. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr discs using a Perkin Elmer-621 spectrometer. Electron spin resonance spectra for the complexes were recorded with a Varian-4502 spectrometer on powdered sample and of ethanolic solution at room temperature. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on powdered sample using a Guoy balance.

Results and Discussion

All these complexes are greenish-yellow to yellow in colour and are highly soluble in alcohol and acetone. Alcoholic or acetone solution of these complexes imparts greenish yellow colour and addition of methanolic silver nitrate does not give any immediate precipitation, but silver is deposited on standing. The molar conductivity values of these complexes are in favour of their non-electrolytic nature (Table 2).

TABLE 2—SOME PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	ΔM ($\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	g
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})]$	Khaki	15.3	1.74	—
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(o\text{-phen})]$	Olive green	12.7	1.73	1.970
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{dipy})(\text{py})]$	Yellow	13.6	1.73	—
$[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(o\text{-phen})(\text{py})]$	Yellow	12.9	1.74	1.978

The infrared spectral bands and their tentative assignments for these complexes are presented in Table 1. The appearance of a strong band in the region $1700\text{--}1710\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a very strong band in the region $2070\text{--}2080\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu(\text{NO}^+)$ and $\nu(\text{CN})$ respectively which are in accordance with the assignments made for the reported complexes^{1,5,6}. The bands at $600\text{--}625$ and $565\text{--}595$ can be assigned to $\nu(\text{Cr-N})$ and $\delta(\text{Cr-N-O})$ respectively as reported by Miki⁷ and the present

author^{2,3}. The coordination of organic molecules to chromium is indicated by shifts in the ligand(s) bands in the spectra of these complexes from their positions in the spectra of the free ligands. Similar shifts on complexation have been reported on several metal complexes using these ligands⁸⁻⁹.

The magnetic moments of all the compounds and g values for a representative set of complexes are presented in Table 2. The magnetic moment values of 1.73 to 1.74 B. M. at 303°K for these complexes and g values of 1.970 and 1.978 for a representative set of complexes of undiluted powdered form, which are comparable to the reported compounds^{2,3,4}, are consistent with a low-spin d^5 configuration of Cr(I).

The analytical data and all the above results suggest the formulation of these complexes as $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})]$ and $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})(\text{py})]$ ($\text{B} = \text{dipy}$ or $o\text{-phen}$). The thiocyanate group may coordinate to the metal through either the nitrogen or the sulphur atom or both. Chromium being in the first transitional series, has been placed as class 'A' metal¹⁰. On coordination $\nu(\text{CN})$ of NCS^- is lowered in N-bonded complexes than in the S-bonded complexes¹¹. A comparison of the observed $\nu(\text{CN})$ with those of the known thiocyanato complexes⁶ suggest N-bonded thiocyanate group in these complexes. The use of $\nu(\text{CS})$ to say more about the nature of coordination could not be possible here because of the presence of several other bands originating from the organic ligands in this region. However, the greater complexity in the esr spectra (ethanolic solution) suggests coordination through nitrogen.

The penta coordinated $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})]$ complexes are assumed to be monomeric. This may be attributed to the lack of chromium to coordinate through sulphur of the thiocyanate group. This is expected having regard to the classification of chromium as a class 'A' metal¹⁰. The inclusion of pyridine at the sixth site forming hexacoordinated

complexes $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})(\text{py})]$ also favours the monomeric nature. Thus, it is plausible to propose a square based pyramidal geometry to $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})]$ on the basis of our reported result² and an octahedral geometry to $[\text{CrNO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{B})(\text{py})]$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. B. Singh, Principal and Sri Jagpat Singh, President of the College for facilities and encouragement. Their thanks are also due to Dr. S. Sarkar, Reader, I.I.T., Kanpur and Prof. W. U. Malik, Vice Chancellor, University of Kashmir for encouragement and to Mr. S. C. Chaurasia of BARC for help in spectral studies.

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